

Data Postprocessing Algorithm for Sensor Network in Flood Early Warning Systems

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Abstract: Climate change is intensifying hydrological extremes, increasing the frequency and severity of flood events and placing growing demands on flood early warning systems (FEWS). The reliability of FEWS critically depends on the availability of continuous and high-quality hydrological observations; however, operational monitoring networks frequently suffer from data gaps, anomalies, and sensor failures, particularly during extreme events. This paper presents an innovative data-driven methodology for hydrological time series post-processing, aimed at reconstructing missing water level observations using an ensemble of machine learning models. The proposed approach integrates forecasting and backcasting models based on LSTMs, CNNs, and TCNs, with feature selection guided by hydrological and hydraulic principles. The methodology is developed and tested within a FEWS for the Kolubara catchment in Serbia. Results demonstrate robust reconstruction performance, especially during rising water level conditions, highlighting the method's suitability for operational flood forecasting applications.

Keywords: missing data, machine learning models, LSTM, CNN, TCN, ensemble, forecasting, backcasting

1. Motivation

Climate change is intensifying flood events worldwide. This trend poses substantial risks to human safety, critical infrastructure, and socio-economic stability, while challenging the reliability of traditional flood risk assessment and management approaches. In this context, flood early warning systems (FEWS) have become an essential component of climate change adaptation strategies, enabling timely detection of hazardous conditions and supporting proactive decision-making. The effectiveness of FEWS critically depends on high-quality hydrological observations and reliable real-time data processing.

FEWS are constrained by observational data quality and availability. Hydrological monitoring networks are exposed to sensor malfunctions, communication outages, power failures, and environmental disturbances. As a result, real-world hydrological time series often contain gaps, spurious measurements, and non-physical anomalies that can severely degrade the performance of forecasting models and decision-support tools. Conventional quality control and gap-filling techniques, typically based on simple interpolation or rule-based filtering, are often insufficient to capture the complex, non-linear, and non-stationary dynamics of hydrological processes. This has created a strong demand for advanced data post-processing algorithms capable of robustly detecting anomalies, reconstructing missing observations, and preserving physically consistent system behavior, thereby ensuring the reliability and operational resilience of flood early warning systems (Gaddam et al. 2020, Kim et al. 2025).

Recently, machine learning (ML) has emerged as a promising paradigm for addressing data quality challenges in hydrological applications, owing to its ability to learn complex, nonlinear relationships directly from data. This research introduces an innovative data post-processing approach for hydrological time series that integrates an ensemble of ML models coupled with hydrology domain knowledge to perform anomaly detection and data reconstruction. The approach is developed within FEWS for Kolubara catchment and tested at Tamnava sub-catchment.

2. Materials and methods

Overview

This research presents an algorithm for reconstructing missing data in head hydrographs using an ensemble of sequence forecasting and backcasting ML models (Figure 1). The proposed approach is built upon a database of pretrained models designed to predict hydrological sequences in both forward and backward temporal directions, enabling robust reconstruction of data

gaps under varying flow conditions. The model ensemble comprises Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), and Temporal Convolutional Networks (TCN), selected for their demonstrated effectiveness in capturing temporal dependencies and nonlinear dynamics in hydrological time series (Vinokić et al. 2025). By combining multiple architectures within a unified framework, the algorithm aims to improve reconstruction accuracy, enhance robustness to data uncertainty, and support operational deployment in flood early warning systems.

Case study

The proposed methodology was developed within a FEWS for the Kolubara catchment in Serbia and tested on the Tamnava pilot sub-catchment (Figure 2). The pilot catchment is equipped with four rain gauges and six hydrological gauging stations for continuous water level monitoring (1 hour time resolution). The algorithm is applied to the post-processing of water level time series and evaluated under a controlled hypothetical test scenario in which three gauging stations are assumed to be faulty, resulting in continuous data gaps of three months. This experimental setup enables a systematic assessment of the algorithm's capability to reconstruct missing observations under realistic operational conditions.

Figure 2. Tamnava pilot subcatchment with a scenario of 3 faulty sensors

Figure 1. ML-based framework for hydrological data post-processing

Forecasting and backcasting ML models

Missing data imputation in water level time series is performed by estimating the missing sequences using an ensemble of ML-based forecasting and backcasting models. Feature selection for all models is guided by hydrological and hydraulic principles, ensuring physical consistency and interpretability. For each of the six gauging stations, forecasting models are trained using upstream information, including water level from one or multiple gauging stations and/or rainfall data (Eq. 1). Conversely, backcasting models are constructed using water level data from one or multiple downstream stations as inputs (Eq. 2). This bidirectional modeling strategy enables robust reconstruction of missing sequences by exploiting both spatial and temporal dependencies within the monitoring network.

$$\{Z_i^{t_0+1}, Z_i^{t_0+2}, \dots, Z_i^{t_0+N}\} = f\left(Z_i^{t_0-M}, \dots, Z_i^{t_0}, Z_{i-1}^{t_0-M}, \dots, Z_{i-1}^{t_0}, P_j^{t_0-M}, \dots, P_j^{t_0}, \dots, P_j^{t_0-M}\right) \quad (1)$$

$$\{Z_i^{t_0-N}, Z_i^{t_0-(N-1)}, \dots, Z_i^{t_0-1}\} = f\left(Z_{i+1}^{t_0}, Z_{i+1}^{t_0+1}, \dots, Z_{i+1}^{t_0+M}, Z_{i+2}^{t_0}, \dots, Z_{i+2}^{t_0+M}, \dots\right) \quad (2)$$

Data reconstruction algorithm

Data reconstruction algorithm (Figure 3) utilizes the ensemble of pre-trained ML models for each gauging station where data gap in timeseries has been identified. Each model gives its estimation of the missing sequence while final estimation is based on choosing the ensemble representative (e.g. mean or median values).

3. Results and Discussion

The proposed methodology is tested on a hypothetical scenario in which three sensors (gauging stations Novaci, Čemanov most, and Ub) are completely without data for a period of three months, while the remaining stations exhibit periodic gaps in their time series. The data reconstruction algorithm employs an ensemble of more than 100 pre-trained machine learning models for each gauging station, generated by combining different feature sets and model types. The results (Figure 4) demonstrate that the algorithm can effectively estimate missing data, particularly during periods of rising water levels, which is critical for flood forecasting.

Figure 4. Comparison of reconstructed timeseries (blue lines) and true timeseries (red dotted lines)

4. Conclusions

This approach aims at providing reliable hydrological timeseries used in operation flood forecasting and water resources management. The proposed algorithm demonstrates the potential for dealing with missing data, even when there are months of missing data in timeseries. The ensemble strategy within the proposed algorithm supports integration of additional ML models which may further improve the overall performance of the algorithm.

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